

TEACHING STUDENTS TO COMPOSE A STORY IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: This article is about oral and written story creation by elementary school students.

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Unlike the story that the students read, the picture shows only what to write about. It is not specific vocabulary material. Therefore, in the connected speech exercise, making a story based on a picture is more complicated than making a story based on the text read. . The work of teaching to create a story based on a picture is carried out on the basis of increasing the independence of students. , finally, students begin to write independently, without retelling the story created as a team.

An even more independent, creative work is to write sentences about what they saw during excursions and walks, about the weather, about what was done in the garden or on the school plot. These are some sentences about a common topic. These sentences are not yet connected to each other, and they can be easily replaced. For example, the student wrote about the change of nature in spring, first fruit trees bloom, they turn white, red, pink, and then gardens are covered with blue grass. By changing their places, it is explained which of the objects of observation will appear before and which after.

It is very important to teach students how to choose material for their stories when doing such work. For example, students learn a lot about what they gathered to go on an excursion to nature, what they saw on the way, what they observed in the field, what they saw and heard on the way back. But they cannot tell all of them orally in the form of a coherent text. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to choose the material, that is, to decide what to write about and what not to write about. they decide not to write about. In this way, when the story material is limited, the teacher will clarify it again. During the excursion, he says what he saw and heard about what to write about: nature and weather have changed, the sun is shining brightly, fields and gardens are covered with blue grass, they saw fruit trees and

their flowers. Pupils discuss with the teacher about what they see: what to say about nature and air, then about sunlight, then grass in fields and gardens, etc. they can figure out how to make a sentence about.

Such work is a good preparation for creating a story based on live observations. Now students are taught to write a structured story correctly. Remembering the spelling of certain words and phrases, asking the teacher to write the words that you do not know the spelling of in the process of writing is emphasized.

The story "Izzat's Chicks" is given in the mother tongue and reading literacy textbook.

Izzat's chicks

Munisa was bored at home alone. When she looked out of the yard, her neighbor Izzat's door was open.

- Glory! Munisa called. Izzat smiles at him.

"Remember, you wanted to show your chicks," he said.

"Come on, I'll show you," said Izzat.

Izzat took Munisa to the chicken room. - We have five chicks. They are the children of the yellow hen.

There was a big yellow chicken in the cage. His chicks were chirping by his side. The mother hen would rummage and find something for them. He saw the children and immediately got up. The chicks quickly hid in his pants.

"Your hen is hot," said Munisa, "I wanted to see the chicks."

"If we hide for a while, the children will come out again," said Izzat.

They were hiding a little. Then the chicks came out of their mother's nest one by one. Munisa stared at them.

After the story is read, it is analyzed with the help of the teacher. Retelling is carried out with the help of students. To strengthen the text, the answers to the questions below the text are found: What do you do when you are bored? What did

Izzat tell Munisa about? How many children does the yellow hen have? Why is the mother hen crying? Where did the chicks hide? How did the children avoid scaring the chicks? Did Munisa see the chicks?

After the answers to the questions are found with the help of the students, now the story plan is made and the students are asked to write what they know.

It is not mandatory to require students to write the plot of the story completely. Every student should write as much as possible. Independent writing of one sentence about a story can also be considered a good achievement.

The exercise of answering the question based on what was read in the 1st grade by creating a small story with a few sentences is quite complicated. For this type of exercise, not only pictures are used, small stories read, what the students have seen as a team (materials about an excursion, a walk, going to the city, going out to the village, school events) are also sources. When working on creating a story based on a picture, it is appropriate to use a series of pictures. The series of pictures serves as a plan for the students' story. In the task "Determine the sequence of events in the fairy tale. Write in your notebook" several fairy tale pictures are given. Students carefully study the picture first and make a small story based on the picture.

"Goats were grazing in the meadow. The evil wolf wanted to eat them. Serkabobo asked the lion for help. The lion also wanted to harm them. Serkabobo punished the lion." they write sentences.

In the 2nd grade, students work on the basis of the stories and texts given in the Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy textbook. During the lesson, they also write the necessary instructions and tasks in the exercise book.

At the same time, they practice creating a short story based on a plan. Students are taught the importance of using information in addition to what is read. The main purpose of story telling based on a plan is explained.

In the 2nd grade, students find an answer to one question based on what they have read. The answer is first prepared orally as a team. For example, based on the plan made by the team for the story "Shippak" by M. Hamidova, each question is expanded with several sentences. What kind of boy is Firdaus? Who will be Princess Firdaus? How did you imagine the family of Firdaus? How many people do you think live in this household and who are they? What does the sound of thunder sound like? Why did mother move the tea from cup to cup?" The team can answer the questions in different ways. The first question, "What kind of boy is Firdaus?", "Sleepy boy", "Lazy boy", "Lazy boy" can be answered.

This type of exercise teaches students to choose the appropriate sentences for the answer from the text. Often, using only some words in the sentence, you have to enter your own words and make sentences to find the answer. All work similar

to the one given above from connected speech is educational in nature and provides an opportunity to prepare for a written story on the basis of an oral story. compared to the written statement, it is a more independent work, it prepares to compose independent sentences based only on the picture.

You can prepare for writing a story on "Our School" as follows:

1. They talk about what they know about the school building, classroom equipment, teachers and students. They can also talk about other conditions created in the school: Our school is called the "school of champions" because world champions in such sports as swimming, wrestling, gymnastics and chess study here.

2. They also write about the school's garden, kitchen, sports ground. They write some words and phrases in their notebooks: school garden, our school kitchen.

3. They write some thoughts about their educational experience in their notebooks, this is an independent work in the period of preparation for writing a story. In oral storytelling, students must: 1) speak in an orderly manner based on a certain plan and in a certain sequence; 2) in order to write a complete and correct story, they are trained to compose sentences that they can write independently.

When teaching students to write stories in the 2nd grade, they build on the knowledge and skills they acquired in the 1st grade. In this class, students begin to write stories independently, they also get elementary theoretical knowledge about what a story is, how to prepare for writing it.

The school's experience shows that the most common defect in the stories of 3rd graders is that the content of the story does not correspond to the set topic. For example, in the story titled "Spring", students write about how they spent a day in the spring, "The Wide Field" and in the story on the subject, they write about a walk to the fields. However, they do not write about the image of nature, the view of the fields in spring, they hardly use visual means in their work.

In their stories on "My favorite animal", the students wrote about the types of animals using only one or two visual aids: I keep a cat at home. A cat is a smart and sensitive animal. I pet the cat. He loves me too.

The most noticeable shortcoming in children's stories is the lack of connection between parts of the story. In the story, each part is connected in terms of content and structure, and sentences should be structured correctly in terms of content and grammar. . If these rules are not followed, it will be a collection of some sentences that are not connected in thought.

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